

Review on Handwriting Recognition Techniques

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Abstract- Handwriting is a skill that is unique to every individual. It was developed long time ago as a means to expand memory and facilitate communication. Handwriting of every person differs from every other. Every individual has their own style of writing. The understanding of handwriting generation is important in the development of both on-line and off-line recognition systems. Online handwriting recognition deals with information about writing dynamics as the text is being written while offline handwriting recognition deals with static information. This paper serves as a guide and updates the readers working on handwriting recognition. Here we are giving the review of some of the methods for handwriting recognition from selected papers.

Keywords: Handwriting recognition, Online, Offline, Static, Dynamic.

I. Introduction

The history of handwriting recognition systems is not complete without mentioning the Optical Character Recognition (OCR) systems which preceded them. Optical Character Recognition (OCR) is a problem recognized as being as old as the computer itself. There have been many papers and technical reports published reviewing the history of OCR technologies

Modern OCR was said to have begun in 1951 due to an invention by M. Sheppard called GISMO, a robot reader-writer. In 1954, a prototype machine developed by J. Rainbow was used to read uppercase typewritten letters at very slow speeds. By 1967, companies such as IBM finally marketed OCR systems. However in the late 60's, these systems were still very expensive, and therefore could only be used by large companies and government agencies. Today, OCR systems are less expensive and can recognize more fonts than ever before. Even so it is important to note that in some situations these commercial packages are not always satisfactory. Senior mentions that problems still exist with unusual character sets, fonts and with documents of poor quality.

Research now focuses more on hand-printed numeral, character and joined/cursive handwriting recognition. Unfortunately the success of OCR could not carry on to handwriting recognition, due to the variability in people's handwriting. This created opportunity for research scholars to perform handwriting recognition using various techniques.

The paper consists of 4 sections. Section 1 includes introduction to handwriting recognition. Section 2 surveys research carried out by various research scholars. Section 3 describes various techniques used for handwriting recognition. Finally paper ends with conclusion in section 4.

II. Related work

Suen [1] mentions that the key to handwriting recognition rates is feature extraction. However, this in itself is a very difficult problem which has led researchers to use more complex methods for pre-processing, feature extraction and classification. Such methods include the use of Neural Networks and Mathematical Morphology such as HMM.

In some cases, researchers have constrained their experiments heavily, only using one person's handwriting, while other researchers' experiments were not performed on benchmark databases.

Some of the problems and challenges which are faced by researchers today include: developing accurate segmentation, pre-processing, feature extraction and classification techniques. For the first problem, segmentation, the diverse styles and sizes of handwriting both play a large factor in the failure of current techniques. In some cases even a human being would not be able to segment handwriting containing characters which are tightly packed together and illegible. These segmentation systems also have to deal with the variability of handwriting from one person to another, not to mention problems when one writer's handwriting is cursive, while another person's is simply overlapping. Challenges faced for pre-processing deal with the choice of whether to convert raw handwriting into a more efficient form i.e. whether to keep handwriting in grey-scale form or binary form.

The segmentation of written words into component characters is often the first step in handwriting recognition systems. In some cases, segmentation is forced on the user by providing boxes for the writing of discrete letters. However in modern era continues speech recognition efforts, segmentation of phonemes is not performed either before training or the recognition steps. Instead segmentation occurs simultaneously with recognition. If such a system is adapted for handwriting recognition, the very difficult issue of time consuming would be avoided.

The method described in [2] uses combination of template and feature matching technique to recognize the pre segmented character shapes using neural networks. Neural Network approach is also used for classification and recognition, since writing have a high input dimension and presence of large number of weights in the network. Next they used the sequence of angle features and single hidden layer network for classification, but the performance of these systems was also poor. Main reason for the poor performance the presence of noise in the x-y coordinates, which affected the extracted features greatly.

In Paper [3] proposes a recognition system for handwritten manuscripts by writers of the 20th century. The proposed system first applies some pre-processing steps to remove background noise. Next the pages are segmented into individual text lines. After normalization a hidden Markov model based recognizer, supported by a language model, is applied to each text line. Paper [3] investigates two approaches for training the recognition system. The first approach consists of training the recognizer directly from scratch, while the second adapts it from a recognizer previously trained on a large general off-line handwriting database. The second approach is unconventional in the sense that the language of the texts used for training is different from that used for testing. In paper [3] experiments with several training sets of increasing size found that the overall best strategy is adapting the previously trained recognizer on a writer specific data set of medium size. The final word recognition accuracy obtained with this training strategy is about 80%.

Character recognition has been the subject of intensive research for more than thirty years. However, the problem of handwritten character recognition is far from being satisfactorily resolved despite many research efforts. The greatest difficulty lies in the infinite variations of shapes resulting from the writing habits and styles of the different writers. Stochastic modelling is a flexible and general method for modelling such problems in which dealing with uncertain information is necessary. Hidden Markov Model (HMM) has become the most promising model in speech recognition, mainly due to its ability to handle the sequential dynamic speech signal. Because of this success, it is naturally expected to achieve similar success in handwriting recognition. [4] Propose an efficient scheme for Chinese handwriting recognition in the framework of HMM.

Automatic identification of handwritten script facilitates many important applications such as automatic transcription of multilingual documents and search for documents on the Web containing a particular script. The increase in usage of handheld devices which accept handwritten input has created a growing demand for algorithms that can efficiently analyse and retrieve handwritten data. [5] Paper proposes a method to classify words and lines in an online handwritten document into one of the six major scripts: Arabic, Cyrillic, Devanagari, Han, Hebrew, or Roman. The classification is based on 11 different spatial and temporal features extracted from the strokes of the words. The proposed system attains an overall classification accuracy of 87.1 percent at the word level with 5-fold cross validation on a data set containing 13,379 words. The classification accuracy improves to 95 percent as the number of words in the test sample is increased to five, and to 95.5 percent for complete text lines consisting of an average of seven words.

It is well known that Hidden Markov Models (HMM) and Dynamic Programming (DP) [6], provide a theoretical framework and practical algorithms for temporal pattern recognition with lexical constraints (even for large vocabularies). The techniques initially developed for ASR are also applicable to Handwriting Recognition (HWR), which shares many features with ASR especially if auto segmentation (from word to letter) is used. Most on-line cursive handwriting recognition systems use a lexical constraint to help improve the recognition performance.

In Paper [7], an integrated offline recognition system for unconstrained handwriting is presented. The proposed system consists of seven main modules: skew angle estimation and correction, printed handwritten text discrimination, line segmentation, slant removing, word segmentation, and character segmentation and recognition, stemming from the implementation of already existing algorithms as well as novel algorithms. This system has been tested on the NIST, IAM-DB, and GRUHD databases and has achieved accuracy that varies from 65.6% to 100% depending on the database and the experiment.

Most of Arabic handwriting recognition in previous works focused on recognizing offline script [8]. Much of online recognition focused on isolated Arabic letters only. As far as we could determine, there was little work that tackled the difficulties of online Arabic cursive handwriting recognition. Alimi and Usher developed an online Arabic handwriting recognition system based on decision-tree techniques. The system was tested with 13 Arabic-letter shapes. Alimi developed an online writer dependent system to recognize Arabic cursive words based on Neuro fuzzy approach. The system was tested by one writer on 100 replications of a single word.

As for the delayed strokes, previously work viewed them as features that added complexity to online handwriting recognition. Four methods were proposed to recognize words with delayed strokes. In the first method, delayed strokes were totally discarded from handwriting in the pre-processing phase [8]. In the second, delayed strokes were detected in the pre-processing phase and then used in a post processing phase [8]. In the third method, the end of a word was connected to the delayed strokes with a special connecting stroke. This special stroke, which indicated that the pen was raised, resulted in a continuous stroke sequence for the entire handwritten English sentence. Finally, delayed strokes were treated as special characters in the alphabet. So, a word with delayed strokes was given alternative spellings to accommodate different sequences where delayed strokes are drawn in different orders.

The research of on-line handwriting recognition started in the 1960s and has been receiving intensive interest from the 1980s. The comprehensive survey before 1990s is made in [9]. As recent survey papers, Plamondon et al. mainly reviewed the status of western on-line handwriting recognition while Liu et al. and Jaeger et al. reviewed that of on-line Chinese and Japanese handwriting recognition. Papers [9] mainly discuss on-line Japanese handwriting recognition.

Paper [10] uses three different feature extraction methods for handwriting recognition, such as Geometric Moment Invariant (GMI), United Moment Invariant (UMI), and Zernike Moment Invariant (ZMI) and compares the performance of all three methods on same dataset and classifier. The dataset is Char74K and classifier is support Vector Machine (SVM). The combined GMI-UMI-ZMI features provided the recognition up to 96% of the level of accuracy using SVM-RBF kernel and 89% using PuK kernel.

Paper [11] studied the hidden control neural network and proposed a HCNHMM hybrid approach for on-line cursive handwriting recognition. They applied HCNHMM at the HMM state level and handwriting primitives were precisely modelled and different writing styles were described in terms of control signals. HMM chain was used at the letter level to organize different primitives and obtained 80.4% efficiency.

The research [12] proposes real time handwriting mathematic expression recognition based on HMM. The system evaluates the performance based on feature extraction techniques. The result shows that average recognition rates of using Pen Up/Down, Normalized Y-Coordinate, Vicinity Slope, Curvature features are the highest at 71.84%, following by using Pen Up/Down, Normalized Distance to stroke edge, Normalized Y-Coordinate, Vicinity at 71.48% and using five features at 70.03%.

Paper [13] proposes the use of hybrid Hidden Markov Model (HMM)/Artificial Neural Network (ANN) models for recognizing unconstrained offline handwritten texts. The structural part of the optical models has been modelled with Markov chains, and a Multilayer Perceptron is used to estimate the emission probabilities. This paper also presents new techniques to remove slope and slant from handwritten text and to normalize the size of text images with supervised learning methods. Slope correction and size normalization are achieved by classifying local extreme of text contours with Multilayer Perceptron. Slant is also removed in a non uniform way by using Artificial Neural Networks.

III. Handwriting recognition techniques

A. Optical character recognition(OCR)

OCR is the method of converting handwritten or printed text into machine-encoded text, whether from a scanned document, a photo of a document, a scene-photo or from subtitle text superimposed on an image. It is widely used as a form of information entry from printed paper data records, whether passport documents, invoices, bank statements, computerized receipts, business cards, mail, printouts of static-data, or any suitable documentation. It is a common method of digitizing printed texts so that they can be electronically edited, searched, stored more compactly, displayed on-line, and used in machine processes such as cognitive computing, machine translation, text-to-speech, key data and text mining. OCR is a field of research in pattern recognition, artificial intelligence and computer vision.

B. Neural Network

Neural network (NN) is a discriminative classifier in that all in class and out of class data are used in the training. NN body of literature is enormous because it has been used widely in many areas. NN have been used in handwriting recognition system with success. However, compared to HMM, they require more computation. In addition, and of more importance, is that, they are not able to model time variations in handwriting signal, which is important for word recognition. They are static classifiers which require fixed size feature vector. Due to that, they are normally used only in character or digit recognition. There are also some other weaknesses of NN as a discriminative classifier, some of which are as follows.

- a) In term of generalization property, NN is known to over fit data unless specific measures are taken to avoid that although cross validation can be done to avoid that, it is quite hard to achieve good generalization when only a limited amount of training data is available.
- b) The optimization process in gradient-based NN learning is according to the principle of empirical risk minimization (ERM) using the back-propagation (BP) algorithm. Though this guarantees good performance on the training data, performance on the test data is difficult to obtain.

- c) Choosing Model Topology is another issue. In most connectionist system, the topology is needs to be fixed prior to training Often; this requires some expert knowledge of the data. Learning the topology automatically is possible but quite time and resource consuming.
- d) Training Convergence is considerably slower (as compared to ML estimation in HMM). Infact, NN training does not guarantee global optimum

C. Support Vector Machine

A support vector machine (SVM) is machine learning algorithm that analyzes data for classification and regression analysis. SVM is a supervised learning method that looks at data and sorts it into one of two categories. An SVM outputs a map of the sorted data with the margins between the two as far apart as possible. SVMs are used in text categorization, image classification, handwriting recognition and in the sciences.

A good classifier needs to have good generalization, minimum risk, better convergence properties and better discrimination power and possess a model topology that does not have to be fixed a priori. This has led to the support vector machines (SVM).

SVM had been proven to generalize well. SVM generalization properties allows for a bound on performance on a given test set to be part of the training process without having to actually test the system. Normally, empirical risk minimization (ERM) as used in NN is the most common optimization criteria used to estimate classifiers. However, using ERM, the solution is not unique. There are several configurations of the classifier that can achieve minimum risk specified in the ERM, on the training set (as seen in NN training). There is a need to decide on the configuration that has the least upper bound on the expected test set error. This is the principle of structural risk minimization (SRM). Support vector machines are based on this principle. With SRM, a classifier will have the least expected risk on the test set and therefore a good generalization.

D. Graph theory

The acquired data we can construct mathematical graph of data. Graph is the main concept of the graph theory. In our case, undirected weighted graphs will be used. The first feature that we need to extract from the graph is the information whether the graph is connected or not. Graph is connected if we choose one vertex and traveling along the edges of the graph manage to reach all other vertices of the same graph. In the computer science this can be achieved by implementing „light versions“ of Depth-First Search or Breadth-First Search algorithms which will tell us if they have searched through all the graph vertices. This will be the main factor for the best match scoring in the identification process.

The connectivity of a given graph will be very important in determining next graph features. We want to know is the graph Euclidian or has the graph Euler path (Euclidian trail). Rare mathematical graphs are Euclidian graphs, thus if someone's signature produces that kind of graph it would certainly be of the great influence to the identification process. Graph is Euclidian if and only if all the vertices have an even degree (degree of the vertex is the number of edges connected with the vertex).

E. Recurrent neural network

The Feed forward neural networks (FNN) have an important drawback: only a fixed number of previous words can be taken into account to predict the next word. This limitation is inherent to the structure of FNNs, since they lack any form of 'memory': only the words that are presented via the fixed number of input neurons can be used to predict the next word and all words that were presented during earlier iterations are 'forgotten', although these words can be essential to determine the context and thus to determine a suitable next word. In order to overcome these problems we preferred for RNN.

The context length was extended to indefinite; one could even say infinite, size by using a recurrent version of neural networks, conveniently called recurrent neural networks (RNN), which can handle arbitrary context lengths. Initial enthusiasm about RNN as statistical language modellers, mainly driven by their abilities to learn vector representations for words (as in FNN) and to handle arbitrarily long contexts, in addition to the fact that they are universal approximates was quickly tempered by their extremely slow learning and by the observation that Computer Speech and Language the theoretical incorporation of arbitrarily long context lengths does not manifest itself in practice. Consequently, many variations on the original RNN have been developed to cope with these limitations and, at the same time, to specialize their structure towards SLM.

Main RNN architectures that resulted from the attempts to turn the original, theoretically well founded RNN with its limited practical usefulness into more practically oriented structures, where researchers were willing to exchange the theoretical soundness with heuristic reasoning (at least to some degree), but without giving up the aforementioned strengths. Each RNN architecture is compared to the original structure, and empirical evaluations, as done by researchers in the field, are presented.

F. Conventional neural network

Conventional neural networks can be considered the main stream classifier for image data classification. Despite the efforts from the research community to perform visual target recognition and classification using traditional machine learning methods, CNNs rapidly dominated the visual recognition domain with its high accuracy classification results. As in many deep neural network designs, CNNs require minimal *a priori* knowledge on the training data compared to traditional machine learning algorithms. This is a major advantage of using CNNs compared to pre-existing learning methods.

A CNN consists of multiple hidden layers and an input and an output layer. Hidden layers in a CNN consist of convolution layers, pooling layers, fully connected layers and normalization layers. The input (in our case) is the target image to be classified and the output is the context of the image. In addition, there is a cost function used to find the most fitted set of parameters and activation functions to determine the final output.

G. Fuzzy logic

Fuzzy approach to off-line handwritten signature recognition. The solution is based on characteristic feature extraction. After finding signature's center of gravity a number of lines are drawn through it at different angles. Cross points of generated lines and signature sample, which are further grouped and sorted, are treated as the set of features. On the basis of such structures, obtained from a chosen number of learning samples, a fuzzy model is created, called the fuzzy signature.

During a verification phase the level of conformity of an input sample and the fuzzy signature is calculated. The extension in feature extraction as well as proposed fuzzy model has never been employed before. It needs to be emphasized that information stored within the verification system cannot be used to recreate the original signatures collected at the enrolment phase. The fact is particularly valuable for large databases and systems where storage safety is crucial. The solution is very flexible and allows the user to extend an intuitive structure of fuzzy sets by employing dynamic features, making the approach an on-line method. The results obtained should be still improved, similarly to the case of other known biometric systems related to signature recognition.

H. Back propagation network

It is a common method of training artificial neural networks and used in conjunction with an optimization method such as gradient descent. The algorithm repeats a two phase cycle, propagation and weight update. When an input vector is presented to the network, it is propagated forward through the network, layer by layer, until it reaches the output layer. The output of the network is then compared to the desired output, using a loss function, and an error value is calculated for each of the neurons in the output layer. The error values are then propagated backwards, starting from the output, until each neuron has an associated error value which roughly represents its contribution to the original output.

Back propagation uses these error values to calculate the gradient of the loss function with respect to the weights in the network. In the second phase, this gradient is fed to the optimization method, which in turn uses it to update the weights, in an attempt to minimize the loss function. The importance of this process is that, as the network is trained, the neurons in the intermediate layers organize themselves in such a way that the different neurons learn to recognize different characteristics of the total input space.

IV. Conclusion

The paper surveys various handwriting recognition approaches. While comparing the various approaches, it is found that HMM is more efficient for training as HMM algorithms are based on likelihood maximization also HMM do not get affected much with orientation, illumination, size etc of handwriting but has poor discriminative ability and neural network is more efficient technique to improve the accuracy and robustness of the system for classification as it has superior discriminative ability. So that we can conclude that Hybrid of HMM and neural network technique is the best suited for identification of person based on handwriting. In future we can use other high level primitives based on word, line and paragraph.

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